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**Climatic variables affecting the population density of the phytophagous mite
Tetranychus urticae (Acari: Tetranychidae) infesting the common beans
Phaseolus vulgaris plantation**

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Abstract

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Climatic variables affecting the population density of the two-spotted spider mite (TSSM), *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae), were determined in a field of common bean, *Phaseolus vulgaris* L., a plantation. This investigation was conducted over two successive autumn seasons from the second week of September to the first week of December in the years 2021 and 2022 at the Agriculture Research Station located in Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. *T. urticae* populations exhibited pronounced fluctuations throughout the cropping season in relation to variations in average temperature and relative humidity. The initial infestation of *T. urticae* was observed in the second week of September, 13 mites/leaf during the first season, which increased to 158 individuals/leaf during November in the same season. The highest population peak was noticed at 260 individuals/leaf in December of the second season. The results showed that climatic factors such as temperature and relative humidity have a significant impact on the prevalence and population densities of *T. urticae* on the common beans, *Ph. vulgaris* during the second autumn season.

Introduction

The common bean, *Phaseolus vulgaris* L., represents the most important legume within the family Fabaceae, and its genus is named *Phaseolus*. This legume is also the most grown pulse worldwide because of its high protein content, fiber, and other essential minerals for humans (Hayat *et al.*, 2014, and Chávez-Mendoza and Sánchez, 2017). They are essential foods in most tropical and subtropical countries of the world, and they are second, following cereals, as a food source for humans and animals (Graham and Vance, 2003). Legumes are also

necessary for their nitrogen-fixing in soil (Keyser and Li, 1992, and Amannuel *et al.*, 2000) and can be applied in crop rotation systems to improve soil quality. Regarded as an alternative to nitrogen fertilizers that may cause serious environmental disorders (Nason and Myrold, 1992, and Brentrup *et al.*, 2001). Pests and diseases that attack common beans can influence agricultural productivity, resulting in yield losses, particularly in the tropics (Graham and Vance, 2003). The damage caused by the most destructive pests and diseases can be as high as 35% to 100%

each year (Singh and Schwartz, 2010). Diseases such as brown rust and powdery mildew and insect pests such as aphids, caterpillars, leafhoppers, and whiteflies reduce their production.

The two-spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) (TSSM), can attack many crops such as soybean, cowpea, and common bean (Razmjou *et al.*, 2009; Seki, 2016; and Çağatay *et al.*, 2018) and can infest delicious Egyptian fruits (Hussian *et al.*, 2018a). In Egypt, *Tetranychus spp.* can infest a wide range of plants grown in greenhouses and open fields, where favorable environmental conditions can aid in completing its life cycle from eggs to adults under optimal conditions (Biswas *et al.*, 2004). Mites infest beans and can be associated with their soil; nineteen mite species were recognized in soil (Soultan and El-Sharabasy, 2024).

Overuse of acaricides can pose risks to humans, plants, and animals (Wilson, 1993, and Wilson *et al.*, 1991), and it can harm natural predators. Climatic variables like atmospheric temperature and relative humidity are the most critical parameters influencing the abundance of phytophagous mites and their predators (Hussian *et al.*, 2018b).

This study is designed to evaluate the densities and fluctuations of *T. urticae* populations in common bean fields at Ismailia Governorate, Egypt, during the two growing seasons of 2021 and 2022 in correlation to temperature degrees and relative humidity as climatic variables.

Materials and methods

1. Plant sampling:

The investigation was carried out in a common bean field located at Ismailia governorate, Egypt, to estimate the population densities of the two-spotted spider mite *T. urticae* throughout the 2021 and 2022 seasons. The experimental area was cultivated with common beans, *Ph. vulgaris*, and

subdivided into three equal plots. The autumn plantations of *Ph. vulgaris* were sown on 28th August. Normal agricultural practices and little approaches to pesticide treatment were followed.

2. Mite counting:

Collecting of bean leaves started two weeks after planting data and continued until the 1st week of December through two seasons. The occurrence of phytophagous mites was observed and recorded

weekly on *Ph. vulgaris* plants, starting in September and continuing until December over the two years. Thirty common bean *Ph. vulgaris* L. leaves were collected randomly from twenty-five plants and then placed in polyethylene bags labelled with the date of collection, place, and plant; brought to the laboratory of the Plant Protection Department, Agriculture Research Station, Ismailia; and immediately examined by a stereomicroscope. The infested mite species, recognized as the two-spotted spider mite, *T. urticae*, was preserved in Hoyer's medium for conservation in a mite collection box. The data were quantified as the number of adult stages per leaf.

3. Climatic variables:

Records of average temperature and relative humidity degrees were obtained from the Agro-meteorological Station of Ismailia Governorate. TSSM populations were correlated with average temperature and relative humidity by calculating the simple correlation coefficient[®] in order to study the effect of these climate variables on the population density of TSSM by their adult stages on Phaseolus plants during the autumn plantations of both years (2021 and 2022).

Results and discussion

1. Population density of the phytophagous mite, *Tetranychus urticae*, attacking a common bean,

***Phaseolus vulgaris*, during two seasons in Ismailia Governorate:**

The results were recorded over two consecutive autumnal seasons, from the second week of September to the first week of December during the years 2021 and 2022. The results showed that the two-spotted spider mite is infesting common beans, serving as the primary herbivore of *Ph. vulgaris* cultivars, with population peaks coinciding with the common bean's growing period. The results were confirmed by Akhtar *et al.* (2012), who found that the common bean, *Ph. vulgaris*, is attacked by one of the most destructive pests, called the two-spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* (TSSM). This mite can infest many crops, causing annual yield losses of 5% worldwide due to the TSSM herbivory. Other survey studies carried out on *Ph. vulgaris* in summer seasons resemble Abo-Zaid (2011), who showed that the main pests infesting green bean plants during three successive seasons, 2008, 2009, and 2010, in summer plantations were TSSM, which was the most abundant pest, followed by *Liriomyza trifolii* (Burgess)

(Diptera:Agromyzidae), *Aphis craccivora*, Koch (Hemiptera: Aphididae), *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli (Hemiptera : Cicadellidae).

Furthermore, Magouz *et al.* (2011) assessed various *Ph. vulgaris* cultivars and breeding lines for their relative vulnerability to the spider mite *Tetranychus cucurbitacearum* Sayed (Acari: Tetranychidae) and the whitefly *B. tabaci*. *Ph. vulgaris* provides a favorable silk-spinning condition for small herbivore TSSM, shielding its eggs from predators (Navajas *et al.*, 2013 and Sarmiento *et al.*, 2011). Mite fluctuations throughout the cropping season were in direct response to variations in average temperature and

relative humidity (Table 1 and Figures 1 and 2).

Table (2) illustrates that mite infestations were initially noticed during the second week of sampling in September. The maximum peak of TSSM populations was found on 25th November (158 individuals per leaf) during the first season (2021). Over the period of two seasons, the highest peaks of phytophagous mite, *T. urticae* populations, were 200 and 260 individuals/leaf were noticed during the last week of November and the first week of December, as presented in Figure (3). These evaluations of *T. urticae* populations were recorded in the second season of the study. The population growth of TSSM began in early September with thirteen individuals/leaf and then increased to 55 individuals/leaf in late September. In October, population numbers of TSSM reached higher numbers later in the month. The highest population density of mites was recorded 158 individuals/leaf in late November and then decreased again at the end of the cropping season in the first year. Basha *et al.* (2018) estimated that the initial infestation occurred in a few numbers, and climatic factors can affect the population growth of mites. The total population of adults was markedly fewer in the first crop season compared with the second season. Their densities recorded were 485 and 718 individuals, respectively. The initial infestation of TSSM was absent in the first three weeks of the study in the second season. Data in (Tables 1 and 2) explained the variations in population density of the two-spotted spider mite in response to temperature degrees and relative humidity. The highest increase of adult populations (158, 200, and 260 individuals per leaf) was counted on 25th November and 1st December at temperatures of 21.11°C, 20.83°C, and

18.33°C during both seasons (Tables 1 and 2). Glas *et al.* (2014) showed that the optimal conditions can mediate the adult females reaching their body size of around 0.5 mm in length and laying more than 100 eggs during their longevity. While the lowest peak populations of the investigated TSSM decreased, 10 individuals per leaf were noticed in October during the second season. Their average temperature and average relative humidity were 24.4°C and 54.27 percent, respectively. TSSM initial infestations appeared by 13 individuals in the third week of September (when the average temperature and relative humidity were

28.53°C and 57.81% R.H.) to zero individuals per leaf on the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd dates of collection during the second season at the average temperatures of 26.66°C, 28.89°C, and 31.11°C during the 2022 season. The population numbers increased gradually, reaching 260 individuals in the first week of December, which varied this value at 18.33°C and 49.72% R.H. to 50 individuals on the same date. These findings are similar to those of Patil and Nandihalli (2009), who indicated that during the autumn season, more tetranychid mites attack crops and appear at a later stage than summer crops.

Table (1): Climatic parameter data of 2021-2022 during the crop season.

Sample date	Temperature (°C)			Relative Humidity %			Temperature (°C)			Relative Humidity%		
	2021						2022					
	Max	Min	Avg.	Max	Min	Avg	Max	Min	Avg.	Max	Min	Avg
16/9	31.11	23.89	27.59	70	57	62.98	31.11	22.22	26.66	68	52	57.81
23/9	32.7	23.89	28.53	68	57	64.35	33.89	23.89	28.89	68	63	65.96
30/9	31.11	22.78	26.94	70	61	65.41	37.22	25	31.11	73	54	63.7
7/10	30	17.78	23.89	64	57	59.81	27.78	21.11	24.44	57	52	54.27
14/10	32.22	22.22	27.22	70	48	62.49	27.78	20	23.89	63	54	58.43
21/10	27.22	18.89	23.05	59	48	55.23	27.78	20	23.89	64	52	59.57
28/10	32.22	20	26.11	59	48	53.71	27.78	21.11	24.44	68	54	61.52
4/11	27.22	20	23.61	64	55	61.5	25	17.78	21.39	63	50	57.5
11/11	25	18.89	21.94	63	50	57.52	25	17.22	21.11	59	50	55.11
18/11	23.89	17.78	20.83	61	55	59.72	25	17.22	21.11	54	45	49.16
25/11	25	17.22	21.11	59	50	55.94	23.89	17.78	20.83	54	41	48.84
2/12	21.11	15	18.05	52	43	47.98	23.89	12.78	18.33	55	46	49.72

Table (2): Population density of phytophagous mite *Tetranychus urticae* on *Phaseolus vulgaris* during the two autumn seasons (2021-2022) at Ismailia Governorate.

Sampling date	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>		Total
	2021	2022	
16/9	0	0	0
23/9	13	0	13
30/9	55	0	55
7/10	32	10	42
14/10	37	22	59
21/10	28	30	58
28/10	41	53	94
4/11	19	49	68
11/11	56	62	118
18/11	77	92	169
25/11	158	200	358
2/12	50	260	310
Total	485	718	1203

Figures (1 and 2): Records of average temperature and relative humidity during (2021-2022).

Figure (3): Population density of *Tetranychus urticae* on *Phaseolus vulgaris* during 2021-2022 season.

2. Correlation studies between phytophagous mite *Tetranychus urticae* population density on *Phaseolus vulgaris* and climatic variables (Average temperature and RH. %):

The data recorded on the population of spider mite *T. urticae* during the two successive seasons of 2021 and 2022, in open field conditions correlated with climatic variables and their effect on the population peaks. The correlation parameters were carried out between the two spotted spider mite (TSSM) population densities and two recordable weather factors, i.e., average temperature and average relative humidity, and these were presented in (Table 3). The spider mite showed a significant negative correlation with average temperature ($r = -0.526$) and a non-significant negative correlation with average relative humidity ($r = -0.307$). These results were estimated in the first season. These results agree with those obtained by Younes *et al.* (2001), who found a significant negative correlation between the tested weather factors and mite density. On the other hand, the correlation between the population of adult stages of *T. urticae* populations and average temperature was negatively significant ($r = -0.756$), and the relative humidity was also correlated negatively with the population numbers ($r = -0.751$) in the second season. Considering the population density of TSSM adult stages, there was a significant negative

correlation with average temperatures during both the first and the second seasons. There was a non-significant negative correlation between average relative humidity and population of adults ($r = -0.57$) in the first season, in contrast to the second season. These results agree with Chauhan and Shukla (2016), who mentioned that average temperature and relative humidity had a significantly negative and a non-significant positive correlation with average relative humidity with the TSSM population on French beans. Desai *et al.* (2017) supported that populations of mites had a negative, non-significant correlation with average relative humidity. Differently, Singh (1995) clarified that the temperature appeared to be a regulatory factor for the population buildup of TSSM on cowpea. El-Khayat *et al.* (1994) estimated the relative population density of *B. tabaci* stages on leaves of summer and winter vegetable crops at two locations in Qalubiya Governorate (Moshtohor and El-Kanater El Khaireia). In winter crops, the infestation levels were highest during November, followed by December, then dropped sharply during January and February, due mainly to the sharp decrease in temperature. Maximum, minimum temperatures, and maximum relative humidity had a significant positive effect on the population of TSSM on kidney beans (El-Saiedy *et al.*, 2012).

Table (3): Correlation between *Tetranychus urticae* population density and (Temp. and RH. %) during 2021-2022 seasons in Ismailia Governorate.

Climatic parameters	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> population (2021)	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> population (2022)
Average Temperature (°C)	-0.5266	-0.756
Average Relative Humidity	-0.307	-0.751

Climatic factors become one of the most vital trends in life, and they are an indicator for climate change impact on our life processes. It is necessary to determine and observe their values

influencing agriculture and the productivity of crops, preserving food security on earth. One of the most destructive pests, *T. urticae*, has the ability to attack a tremendous variety of

vegetables, field crops, fruits, and ornamental plants. In this study, *P. vulgaris* plants had been infested by this mite during the growing period in the autumn season. The population growth and density of mite populations are influenced by fluctuations in temperature and relative humidity degrees. Optimal temperature ranges (18°C-24°C) correspond to the peak population densities of mites observed. Besides climatic factors, the plant age probably plays an important role in infestation other than the biotic factors (Predators).

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